

Scientific article

An initial study on the environmental value of wind farm control

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Abstract: *The integration of wind energy into the electrical grid significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions by displacing conventional power plants. This study presents a novel data-driven approach to quantify the environmental value of wind energy generation through the Marginal Displacement Factor (MDF), expressed in kgCO₂-equivalent per MWh. The MDF captures changes in emissions resulting from incremental variations in wind energy generation within an energy system, while accounting for the time-dependent fluctuations in grid emissions driven by the generation mix and demand-supply dynamics. Using the German energy system and the offshore wind farm Wikinger as a case study, results reveal substantial variability in the MDF and highlight the positive impact of wind energy on grid emission reduction. Furthermore, findings demonstrate that wake steering based wind farm control for maximum power production can improve the environmental value of a wind farm within the same range as the increase in energy production.*

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